

PRODUCTIVITY OF DEVELOPMENT IN THE SYSTEM OF MUSIC EDUCATION IN HIGHER SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the conditions of the cultural and educational environment in the system of music education in higher education from the point of view of the productivity of the development of creative principles and personality culture, the possibility for students to display their creative abilities and achievements, as well as understanding the significance and relevance of the chosen profession, subsequent social adaptation. In this context, the high level of higher education is considered in its interaction with the society, where the existing educational system reveals the quality, level and content of education and imposes certain requirements on university graduates, primarily in terms of their professional competence and relevance in professional activities.

INTRODUCTION

To determine the conditions for organizing the cultural and educational environment in the system of music education, it is necessary to understand what kind of education can be considered productive and high-quality, what are its characteristics, how to make the necessary additions to the existing educational system.

The Uzbek system of higher education has its own unique achievements recognized in the world. Thus, in terms of the level of knowledge and reproductive skills of graduates of domestic universities, the effectiveness of domestic education not only is not inferior to foreign counterparts, but often exceeds them. The process of reforming Uzbek education from the very beginning was aimed both at achieving

global educational standards and at preserving the best domestic traditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The modern paradigm of education implies, first of all, the development of creative principles and culture of the individual, capable of realizing their potential in changing socio-economic conditions, which serves both the interests of the individual himself and the interests of society (B.G. Ananiev, V Zinchenko, N. N. Poddyakov, L. A. Venger, V. A. Krutetskii, D. B. El'konin, G. A. Tsukerman, and A. A. Melik-Pashaev).

Based on the analysis of pedagogical, psychological, sociological literature, on the results of dissertation research of recent years, as well as on our own pedagogical experience, we believe that such characteristics as the quality level of

education, its democracy and effectiveness, as well as the development of creativity and culture of the individual.

The qualitative level of education can be improved both as a result of progressive changes in the process of its implementation, and by attracting innovative methods of pedagogical science. Essential for achieving a high level of education is the growth of professional skills of teachers, their constant self-development, which for students is a clear example of serving their calling, creative dedication, without which true professional success cannot be achieved.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The requirements for improving the quality of training of specialists predetermined the need to search for innovative methods and teaching methods. At present, the majority of teachers-researchers come to the conclusion that the pedagogical technologies that most fully meet the requirements of quality education are those that put the personality of the student at the center of the entire educational system and are aimed at the versatile and creative development of the personality in the cultural and educational environment. - de, are characterized by a humanistic orientation.

These requirements are met by student-centered technologies that have absorbed the ideas of cooperation pedagogy. The most important place in the pedagogy of cooperation is occupied by the idea of joint creative activity, which can be implemented in the common life of diverse (theatrical, chamber performance, vocal-instrumental, literary-artistic, etc.) student groups.

A high level of education also depends on the degree of its interaction with society,

which dictates its own order for the quality, level and content of education and imposes certain requirements on university graduates, primarily in terms of their professional competence and relevance in real practice.

Among the conditions for ensuring a high quality level of education, it is also necessary to mention its material and technical base, outside of which no significant changes in the educational process are possible, since today high-quality education is unthinkable without modern technologies and equipment - audio and video equipment, sound recording and sound reproducing equipment, computer support for the educational process.

One of the most important components of a productive cultural and educational environment in the system of any vocational education is the focus on developing information competence in future specialists, the ability to independently and quickly navigate the system of information resources. The volume of information in the modern world is rapidly increasing, and therefore the possession of the skills of searching, selecting, analyzing and transforming information becomes an integral part of the professional competencies of a music teacher. In the process of modernizing the system of higher education in music education, one of the leading trends is the reduction of classroom hours and the increase in independent work of students. In this regard, competence in the field of information processing significantly increases the quality of a student's self-education.

The information culture of a teacher-musician manifests itself, first of all, in free

orientation in the system of computer technologies, their application not only in terms of visual functions, but also cognitive and didactic ones. In modern conditions, the problem of forming the information culture of a university student requires a transition to a serious pedagogical level. Very constructive, in our opinion, in this area are the scientific research of V.G. Vorobiev, N.I. Gendina, YES. Danilova, N.B. Zinovieva, Yu.S. Zubova, E.A. Medvedeva, K.R. Ovchinnikova, S.M. Oleneva, A.P. Sukhanova, A.I. Black .

One of the most important characteristics of productive and high-quality education is its democratic nature. It lies in the fact that each student has equal rights and obligations, and can count on effective support from teachers and university administration. The democracy of education is also manifested in the activities of student self-government, the opportunity to participate in the public life of the university, in the equal accessibility for each student of all the technical means and information resources that this university has. Within the educational forms in the system of musical education, democracy is most clearly manifested in the process of joint rehearsals, in particular, choral rehearsals. Mutual communication between the teacher and students, the problematic nature of various situations that arise in the process of studying choral compositions, and the joint search for solutions help to create an atmosphere of co-creation and interaction

that is so necessary for a musician. The result of such practical choral lessons should be maximally directed towards creating fruitful creative communication.

Particular attention in the process of creating a productive musical educational environment should be given to the system of interdisciplinary connections. It is very important to think over the system of the so-called "pedagogical logistics", the synchronization of educational modules. This problem is becoming more and more relevant among pedagogical science and requires serious study.

CONCLUSION

Summarizing the foregoing, it can be argued that the organization of productive creative activity of students in the conditions of musical education in higher education should be focused, first of all, on creating a special cultural educational space in the university, which can be characterized as productive. The basis of a productive cultural and educational environment should be considered its characteristics such as the quality level of education, its democracy and effectiveness. They, in turn, should be aimed at:

- development of creative principles and culture of the individual;
- development of the information culture of the future teacher-musician;
- development of research culture, study of advanced pedagogical experience;
- continuous professional growth of the future teacher-musician.

References:

1. Gnatyshina E.V. On the importance of information culture in the process of independent work of students. Psychological and pedagogical research in the education system: 2014; Part 3: 208 - 211.
2. Gribkova O.V. Creative communication in the performing activity of a conductor-choirmaster. Moscow, 2018.

3. Romanova S.E. THE IMPORTANCE OF THE COGNITIVE INFLUENCE OF MUSIC IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE THINKING OF STUDENTS AND STUDENTS AS WELL AS THEY DO IT . ACADEMICIA An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal Vol. 11 , Issue 10, October 2021 <https://saarj.com>
4. Ushakova O.B. Some problems of adjusting the structural and content components of choral classes in the system of training future music teachers. Problems of science and scientific knowledge. Actual problems of the humanities and natural sciences: materials of the I international scientific conference. Moscow, 2015; 4-4: 138-141.